

Polarographic Behaviour of Ferric Iron in Presence of *N,N'*-Dihydroxyethylglycine

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Complexation of Fe^{III} -*N,N'*-dihydroxyethylglycine has been studied employing the techniques of dc polarography, cyclic voltammetry and differential pulse polarography. The method involved the conversion of total iron into ferric form and subsequent complexation with *N,N'*-dihydroxyethylglycine in alkaline medium. Conditions were standardised in which ferric iron gave a distinct d.p. polarographic peak. Estimation of iron in low concentration has been made possible by the dpp technique.

THE standard potential of the reduction reaction, $\text{Fe}^{3+} + e \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{2+}$, is +0.77 V vs NHE which is close to that of the reduction of Hg^{2+} ion (+0.80 V). Therefore, the observed polarographic wave during the reduction of simple Fe^{III} ion is not characteristic of the reduction of ferric ion due to the overlapping of the anodic current resulting from the oxidation of mercury from the dropping mercury electrode (dme)¹. However, in presence of a suitable complexing medium the polarographic reduction of Fe^{III} has been observed and its half-wave potential has been reported. The use of dc polarography to determine ferric iron in the presence of ferrous iron and *vice versa* has been suggested by Meites². Polarographic determination of total iron in a variety of media has also been made by Lingane³. A pulse polarographic method for the determination of ferric and ferrous contents of process streams has been reported in pyrophosphate medium⁴.

In the present investigations, the authors have used *N,N'*-dihydroxyethylglycine, commonly named bicine, as a complexing agent. Dc polarography and cyclic voltammetric methods were employed to study the nature of the reactions while differential pulse polarographic (dpp) technique has been used to evolve a method for determining microamounts of total iron in different water samples.

Experimental

Instrumentation: A PAR polarographic analyser 174-A alongwith a drop timer (model 174/70) and X-Y recorder was used to record dc and differential pulse polarograms. A XY/t recorder alongwith a cyclic voltammetric module (CV-1) (BAS, U.S.A.) was used for recording the cyclic voltammograms. A hanging mercury drop electrode (hmde) was used as the working electrode and a spiral platinum wire was used as the auxiliary electrode. All the potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (sce).

Reagents: All chemicals used were of reagent grade purity. Ferric iron solution was prepared by

dissolving pure iron wire in a small amount of warm nitric acid. The concentration of ferric iron was estimated⁵ volumetrically after reduction to Fe^{II} . Colorimetric estimations of Fe^{III} were made by developing colour with 1:10 phenanthroline⁶. Triple-distilled water was used for preparing solutions. The solutions were deaerated for 20 min by bubbling pure nitrogen. All experiments were done at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

Ferric iron in the presence of bicine in alkaline medium gave two polarographic reduction waves. The first wave showed the reduction of ferric to ferrous form while the second wave indicated the reduction of ferrous to metal. At higher pH (12.00 or more) the second reduction wave appeared to be mixed up with the evolution of hydrogen or cation of the supporting electrolyte. At lower pH (4.00), the polarographic wave could not be identified and only the reduction current due to reduction of Fe^{III} was observed. A typical dc polarogram at pH 9.4 is shown in Fig. 1.

In the former case, the height of second wave was approximately double to that of the first wave. The log-plot analysis for the first wave at pH 10.8 showed a slope value of 0.061 which indicated a reversible one-electron reduction. The influence of mercury pressure on the limiting current was observed by noting the magnitude of limiting current at various heights (h) of mercury column. The observed linearity of current (I_1) vs $\sqrt{h}$ (Fig. 2) indicated that the ferric-bicine system was diffusion-controlled.

It was also observed that at a fixed pH, the half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) did not vary on increasing the concentration of bicine. On the other hand, at a fixed concentration of Fe^{III} and bicine the $E_{1/2}$ was very much dependent on pH of the solution. On increasing the pH, $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards negative potentials. The characteristics of dc polarograms of Fe^{III} in presence of bicine is shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Dc Polarogram containing $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}=1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$, bicine = $0.025 M$; $\text{pH}=9.4$.

Fig. 2. The plot of I_1 vs $\sqrt{h}$; $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}=1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$, bicine = $0.025 M$; $\text{pH}=10.5$, potential of measurement = $-0.80 V$ vs SCE.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF DC POLAROGRAMS OF Fe^{III} IN PRESENCE OF BICINE

Sl. no.	pH	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}=1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$		Bicine = $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$		
		$E_{1/2}$ wave I V	Current wave I μA	I_1/C at -1.0	$E_{1/2}$ wave II V	Current wave II μA
1.	7.50	0.20	0.65	3.42	1.55	1.85
2.	8.00	0.26	0.60	3.16	1.65	1.925
3.	8.55	0.30	0.70	3.68	1.77	1.525
4.	9.40	0.44	0.60	3.16	1.75	1.925
5.	10.00	0.52	0.65	3.42	1.77	1.25
6.	10.8	0.61	0.73	3.80	1.72	1.35
7.	11.45	0.70	0.59	3.10	—	—
8.	12.35	0.81	0.61	3.20	—	—

The plot of pH vs $E_{1/2}$ showed a slope value of 0.13 which indicated that two hydroxyl ions are involved in the reduction process.

Cyclic voltammetry: Cyclic voltammograms were recorded of solutions containing ferric iron and bicine in alkaline medium. The cathodic peak

appeared sharp and well defined, while the anodic peak was rounded. The E_{pc} and E_{pa} were at -0.56 and $-1.03 V$, respectively. The difference of cathodic and anodic peaks ΔE did not coincide with the value for a reversible one-electron reduction. A typical cyclic voltammogram is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram containing $Fe^{III} = 1.9 \times 10^{-4} M$, bicine = $0.025 M$, $NaOH = 0.1 M$; scan rate = $40 mVs^{-1}$.

Differential pulse polarography (dpp): $Fe^{III} \rightarrow Fe^{II}$ reduction wave has been made the basis for the determination of iron contents employing dpp. Fe^{III} in the presence of bicine showed a distinct sharp peak; the peak potential was dependent on pH of the solution. Fig. 4 shows a typical dp polarogram. Conditions were standardised for a method for estimation of total iron at low levels in aqueous matrix. For this purpose, the concentration of bicine was fixed at $0.025 M$ and sodium hydroxide at $0.1 M$. Under these conditions the ferric ion gave a peak at $-0.80 V$. The peak height appeared to be proportional to the concentration of Fe^{III} in the range $0.05-12.8 ppm$.

Estimation of iron in water samples: For the estimation of total iron content, potable, ground and industrial waste water samples were digested with concentrated nitric acid to convert all the iron contents to ferric form. The concentration of bicine and sodium hydroxide were kept 0.025 and $0.1 M$, respectively. The dp polarograms were recorded in the potential range -0.60 to $-1.0 V$. The peak currents were measured at $-0.80 V$ after making

Fig. 4. Dp polarogram of iron; $Fe^{III} = 1 ppm$, bicine = $0.025 M$, $NaOH = 0.1 M$; clock time of pulse = $1 s$, pulse duration = $57 ms$, scan rate = $2 mVs^{-1}$, modulation amplitude = $50 mV$.

blank correction. The iron content in water samples were determined by standard addition method. A large number of water samples (45-50 of each) were analysed in this manner. Results of iron contents in potable, ground and industrial waste water are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. no.	Water sample	Concn. range, ppm	
		Minimum	Maximum
1.	Potable water	0.064	0.85
2.	Ground water	0.072	0.91
3.	Industrial effluents	0.46	2.4

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